

ISic3536

I.Sicily inscription 3536

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

fragment

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Messana

Place of origin (modern)

Messina

Provenance

Necropolis at the Orti della Maddalena

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Messina, Museo regionale
interdisciplinare di Messina, inventory A4951

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI313660

1. Θ (εοῖς) [Κ(αταχθονίους)]

2. ΞΕ [— — — — —]

3. Π [— — — — —]

4. [— — — — —]

5.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 493867

EDCS 38200019

PHI 313660

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 51.1380

Bitto, I. 2001. Le iscrizioni greche e latine di Messina. *Pelorias* 7. Messina. At 28B
undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.
Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità*. At 83 no.3a

Licensed under a Creative

Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-23): ISic3536. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4388730>